

filled or sterile (Fig. c). *D. augustus* was confirmed by microscope examination.

IK36 and IET4094 had only 40% infection; IR50, IET6141, Ratna, Saket

4, China Boro, and IRRI had 80% infection. Disease intensity was 20% less when the same cultivars were partially submerged for 2-3 d.

Because flooding increased ufra incidence, an expected high tide might be used to predict an outbreak in the Gangetic estuarine area. □

Pathogenic variability in *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*

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Bacterial leaf streak (BLS), caused by *X. c.* pv. *oryzicola* (Fang et al) Dye, is an important rice disease in the tropics. Virulence of the bacterium on rice cultivars is not clearly understood. We studied the interaction between the bacterial isolates and the rice cultivars to determine virulence patterns in the Philippines.

Forty-four isolates from various sites in the Philippines were evaluated on susceptible IR50, then 32 isolates were selected and inoculated on 8 IR cultivars. In all experiments, 35-d-old seedlings were spray-inoculated. Virulence was evaluated based on percentage of affected leaf area. Differences among isolates and cultivars were significant, but interaction was not (see table).

To determine the extent of variation in virulence we computed a linear regression. The distribution of virulence of

isolates on test cultivars, based on the regression coefficient (b) and mean percentage of affected leaf area, showed three distinct virulence patterns (see figure). Virulence pattern 1 consisted of seven weakly virulent isolates. Virulence 2 had

intermediate reaction, and virulence 3 was the most virulent to the test cultivars. Isolate BLS 128, from IRRI, was the most virulent and BLS 37, from Isabela, was least virulent. IR38 was resistant to all isolates. □

Scatter diagram of the distribution of 32 *X. campestris* isolates based on regression coefficient (b) and mean percentage of leaf area infection on 8 rice cultivars.

Analysis of variance of partitioned sum of squares^a for isolate of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* and isolate × cultivar effects for percentage leaf area affected, IRRI.

SV	DF	MS	F
Isolate (1) ^d	31	881.702558	2.30**
G ₁	(6)	99.488097	<1
G ₂	(16)	402.660041	1.05 ns
G ₃	(7)	97.320313	<1
G ₁ Vs. G ₂	(2)	9806.023920	25.55**
Vs. G ₃			
Error (b)	31	383.726562	
1 × V	217	121.455294	1.16 ns
G ₁ × V	(42)	40.025510	<1
G ₂ × V	(112)	103.507730	1
G ₃ × V	(49)	124.133450	1.10 ns
Error	(c)217	104.253852	

^a **significant at P = 0.01. G₁ = isolates BLS37, BLS109, BLS88, BLS17, BLS58, BLS53, and BLS45; G₂ = isolates BLS95, BLS2, BLS123, BLS103, BLS102, BLS64, BLS119, BLS130, BLS99, BLS94, BLS64, BLS101, BLS129, BLS93A, BLS66, BLS69, and BLS92; and G₃ = isolates BLS48, BLS124, BLS3, BLS127, BLS128, BLS1, and BLS96.

Efficacy of the systemic fungicide CGA49104 for controlling rice blast (BI)

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We tested the systemic fungicide seed treatments carbendazim 50 WP and CGA49104 50 WP for control of BI under hill conditions at VPKAS farms, Hawalbagh, in 1983 kharif.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. VL501, a BI-susceptible, short-duration variety, was planted in 2.25- × 1.20-m plots under rainfed conditions. Seeds were treated with dry and slurry formulations of the fungicides at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg

seed. Appearance of leaf BI, development until crop maturity, neck BI intensity, and grain yield were recorded for the different treatments: T₁ = untreated check; T₂, T₃, T₄ = dry CGA49104 at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg seed; T₅, T₆, T₇ = CGA49104 slurry at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg seed; T₈, T₉, T₁₀ = carbendazim dry at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg seed; and T₁₁, T₁₂, T₁₃ = carbendazim slurry at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg seed.

Carbendazim was not effective, but CGA49104 at 6 and 4 g ai/kg seed in either form effectively reduced BI intensity and increased yield (Fig. 1, 2). However, CGA49104 was not effective in another experiment where seedlings of Thapachini, a local BI-susceptible variety, were dipped in 125, 250, and 500 ppm concentrations each for 8, 4, and 2 h before transplanting. □

1. Development of leaf BI in different treatments until crop maturity, Almora, India.

2. Percentage of leaf and neck BI and yield levels under different fungicide treatments, Almora, India

Occurrence of sheath blotch (SBI) in India

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SBI, caused by *Pyrenochaeta oryzae* Miyake, is common at light to moderate severity in Ambala, Kurukshetra, Karnal, Sonapat, and Jind districts. In trials at RRS Kaul during 1979 kharif, SBI appeared between maximum tillering and booting on sheaths just below the ligules as a brown spot surrounded by water-soaked areas. Spots bleached in the middle, became milky white, and were studded with numerous black pycnidia (Fig. 1).

Damage varied with variety. On Jaya, symptoms were limited to the sheaths just below the ligules. On Pusa 2-21, the fungus penetrated deep into sheaths and damaged the culm, causing it to break. At RRS Kaul, the disease reduced panicle emergence in late lines PAU 35-5-32 and RP6-56-516 because the base of the flag leaf sheath rotted (Fig. 2).

The pathogen isolated from diseased tissues did not produce pycnidia on PDA, paddy grains, or typha leaves. Three varieties were inoculated at two growth stages: at maximum tillering stage by inserting a rice grain culture or typha leaf-

1. Blotch on sheath with a white center studded with black pycnidia. Note the spot on the junctura and leaf sheath.